

Tahun	Bulan	Total Downtime (Menit)	
		AS-10	AS-11
2018	1	127	0
	2	21	26
	3	3	3
	4	401	134
	5	0	0
	6	0	0
	7	0	0
	8	18	0
	9	6	0
	10	3	0
	11	0	0
	12	0	0
	TOTAL	579	163
	Grand Total	742	

Tahun	Bulan	Total Downtime (Menit)		
		AS-10	AS-11	AS-12
2019	1	35	20	No Line Production
	2	0	2	
	3	64	10	
	4	234	5	
	5	0	0	
	6	13	5	
	7	22	10	
	8	66	0	0

	9	14	2	6
	10	57	0	100
	11	20	13	47
	12	234	0	66
	TOTAL	759	67	219
	Grand Total	1045		

Tahun	Bulan	Total Downtime (Menit)			
		AS-10	AS-11	AS-12	AS-103
		AS-100	AS-101	AS-102	
2020	1	187	126	107	No Line Production
	2	683	21	68	
	3	1225	55	248	
	4	81	5	35	
	5	8	7	5	
	6	26	18	14	
	7	65	5	33	
	8	194	39	210	
	9	258	66	9	24
	10	94	3	68	74
	11	53	14	164	123
	12	163	7	24	72
		TOTAL	3037	366	985
	Grand Total	4681			

Tahun	Bulan	Total Downtime (Menit)
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		AS-100	AS-101	AS-102	AS-103
2021	1	83	4	18	73
	2	70	21	37	26
	3	36	7	125	82
	4	487	122	81	5
	5	18	15	60	5
	6	119	62	55	7
	7	3	1	12	16
	8	18	2	56	28
	9	18	27	19	63
	10	20	23	45	34
	11	17	80	94	3
	12	35	39	44	14
	TOTAL	924	403	646	356
	Grand Total	2329			

Tahun	Bulan	Jumlah line stop			
		AS-100	AS-101	AS-102	AS-103
2022	1	70	124	4	5
	2	44	1	189	0
	3	244	163	38	62
	4	53	128	9	0
	5	74	54	93	77
	6	47	12	61	0
	7	21	29	54	2
	8	11	68	69	77

	9	10	21	97	0
	10	15	12	127	0
	11	16	14	2	56
	12	73	25	15	4
	TOTAL	678	651	758	283
	Grand Total	2370			